

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF QUATERNARY
N-(3-METHYL-2-OXOBUTYL)AMMONIUM HALIDES*

Compd. no.	R	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1a	Pyridinium	140	40	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ INO
1b	Quinolinium	165	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ INO
1c	Isoquinolinium	170	40	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ INO
1d	2-Picolinium	130	30	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ INO
1e	3-Picolinium	148	50	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ INO
1f	4-Picolinium	158	50	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ INO
2a	Pyridinium	200-2	50	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ BrNO
2b	Quinolinium	185-87	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ BrNO
2c	Isoquinolinium	195	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ BrNO
2d	2-Picolinium	130	40	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ BrNO
2e	3-Picolinium	158-60	60	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ BrNO
2f	4-Picolinium	163-65	55	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ BrNO

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and halogen analyses.

Synthesis of some Quaternary β -Ketoalkyl-ammonium Halides as Potential Biochemicals

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A large number of quaternary ammonium halides have been reported to exhibit various biological activities¹. A previous study on the synthesis² of some quaternary β -ketoalkyl ammonium halides as potential antimicrobial agents gave us the necessary impetus to synthesise some new quaternary ammonium halides and evaluate their antifungal activity. We report here the synthesis of a series of N-(3-methyl-2-oxobutyl) quaternary ammonium bromides and iodides (in good yields) by the reaction of 3-methylbut-2-one and halogens (bromine/iodine) with various heterocyclic tertiary bases in isopropanol. Since the preparation of these compounds by known method^{3,4} could not be achieved, we have shown that N-(3-methyl-2-oxobutyl) quaternary ammonium halides could be conveniently synthesised by changing the reaction medium from methanol to isopropanol. These compounds gave the characteristic colour reactions of the enol-betaines (ylids)⁴. The compounds (Table 1) were characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis and spectral data.

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Biological activity: The antifungal activity of these compounds was evaluated at concentrations 50, 100, 500, 1000 and 2000 ppm against *M. phaseoline* and *N. vasinfecta* by poisoned food technique. Compounds 2b and 2d were highly effective against both the fungi at a dose level of 2000 ppm. Rest of the compounds showed moderate activity. The bromides exhibited higher antifungal activity as compared to their corresponding iodides. Introduction of an alkyl substituent on the hetero ring did not appreciably alter the activity.

Experimental

Melting points were taken on a Kofler instrument and are uncorrected. Homogeneity of these compounds was routinely checked by tlc on silica gel G. Electronic and ir spectra were recorded on automatic double beam Speccord and Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometers, respectively, and ¹H nmr spectra (D₂O) on a Varian EM 360 L 60 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference.

Quaternary N-(3-methyl-2-oxobutyl) ammonium iodides (1a-f) and bromides (2a-f): Iodine (0.05 mol) was dissolved in the appropriate heterocyclic tertiary base (0.1 mol). The red-brown solid of the diiodide of the base initially formed was dissolved

on shaking with 3-methylbut-2-one (0.1 mol) in isopropanol (25 ml). The reaction mixture was then refluxed on a water-bath for 5–6 h, then concentrated by distilling off the solvent and left for 3–4 days at 0° when the desired product separated out. Sometimes the product could be separated along with the hydroiodide of the base. Separation from the hydroiodide of the base was affected by fractional crystallisation. The solid so obtained was recrystallised from isopropanol: **1a** λ_{\max} 260 and 226 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400, 2 950–2 850, 1 718, 1 592, 1 460 and 1 380 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.6 (6H, d, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 1.8 (2H, s, CH_2), 3.3 (1H, m, CH) and 8.8–8.9 (5H, m, ArH).

In the case of bromides, bromine (0.1 mol) dissolved in appropriate heterocyclic tertiary base (0.1 mol) was added to an ice-cold solution of 3-methylbut-2-one and the reaction mixture was refluxed and then worked up in an identical manner. Both the quaternary bromides and iodides showed almost the same spectral pattern: **2a** λ_{\max} 265 and 232 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400, 2 980, 1 720, 1 590, 1 462, 1 380; δ 1.6 (6H, d, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 1.8 (2H, s, CH_2), 3.5 (1H, m, CH) and 8.4–9.0 (5H, m, ArH).

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